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Role	Name	Organisation	Date	File suffix
Author	Rosa Chapela	CETMAR	29/03/2022	RC
Author	Duarte F. Vidal	CETMAR	29/03/2022	DV
Author	Sonia Doblado	LDAC	29/07/2021	SD
Author	Alexandre Rodriguez	LDAC	29/07/2021	AR
Author/CS3 Leader	Benvindo Fonseca	IMAR	29/07/2021	BF
Author/CS4 Leader	Mamadou Diallo	COREWAM	29/07/2021	MD
Author/CS5 Leader	Moustapha Bouzouma	IMROP	29/07/2021	MB
Author/CS6 Leader	Vincent Lucas	SFA	29/07/2021	VL
Author	Thiam Ndiaga	ISRA-CRODT	29/07/2021	TN
Author	Fambaye Ngom	ISRA-CRODT	29/07/2021	FN
Author	Yannick Roucou	SFA	29/07/2021	YR
Author	Camara Lamine	IMROP	29/07/2021	CL
Author	Mamadou Dia	IMROP	29/07/2021	MD
Author	Mary Frances Davidson	GROFTP	29/07/2021	MFD
WP leader	Rosa Chapela	CETMAR	29/03/2022	RC
Coordinator	Jónas R. Viðarsson	MATIS	30/03/2022	JRV
Administrative Coordinator	Oddur M. Gunnarsson	MATIS	30/07/2022	OMG

Deliverable D1.5

Summary report from the workshop on “Improving management under fisheries agreements”

30/03/2022

Executive Summary

The relevance of the External Dimension aspects of the EU Common fisheries Policy (CFP) is permanently called into question, casting doubts on whether they are properly integrated within the CFP, evaluating their coherence with other EU policies and estimating their conformity and consistency with the international law of the sea. The relevant branches of this CFP are the so-called 'Sustainable Fisheries Partnerships Agreements (SFPAs) which do represent one of the most pertinent manifestations of the EU's international dimension.

The EU has an enhanced responsibility to promote sustainable and responsible fisheries management in international waters, assuming responsibilities as a contracting party to SFPAs. Those responsibilities range from the reinforcement of governance, to the creation of assessments to strengthen the weaknesses of these agreements by establishing inclusive policies with a real impact on society.

The FarFish project facilitated a web conference/workshop in June 2021 in order to facilitate multi-stakeholder discussions on the advantages, disadvantages and current challenges on the External Dimension of the CFP. The focus of the discussions was on the SFPAs as an instrument to strengthen the collaboration among EU and Coastal States. Organised by Centro Tecnológico del Mar- Fundación CETMAR and the Long Distance Advisory Council (LDAC) the event did offer a mix of panel discussions and different interventions to explore how the CFP External Dimension can be a driver for beneficial change in the field of sustainable fisheries and governance in international waters, in order to improve the implementation of the External Dimension of the CFP in the next period (2023-2033). This report contains a summary of the discussions at the workshop and main conclusions.

From a general view, the conclusions describe a relatively optimistic balance for SFPAs as contributors to sustainable fisheries. Nevertheless, there is still room to improve, especially in order to respond to the needs and interests of coastal states and local communities.

Many of the conclusions formulated during the workshop have assisted the FarFish consortium to feed into a position paper that was submitted to the EC public consultation procedure aimed to inform the revision process of the CFP towards 2022. In addition, some of these recommendations described in the report, are feeding the creation of a policy brief that will be presented at the final FarFish meeting in mid-November 2021, as a new opportunity to generate a strategic document that efficiently encompasses concrete responses and actions towards the CPF review.

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Abbreviations

ACP	African, Caribbean and Pacific Group of States
ANAMER	Asociación Nacional de Armadores de Buques Congeladores de Pesca de Merluza
ANFACO	Asociación Nacional de Fabricantes de Conservas de Pescados
ARVI	Cooperativa de Armadores de Pesca del Puerto de Vigo
CAOPA	Cofédération Africaine des Organisations de Pêche Artisanale
CETMAR	Centro Tecnológico del Mar - Fundación CETMAR
CEPESCA	Confederación Española de Pesca
CFFA	Coalition for Fair Fisheries Arrangements
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy
CNPE	Coalition Nationale de Plaidoyer Environnemental á Madagascar
COMHAFAT-ATLAFCO	Ministerial Conference on Fisheries Cooperation among African States bordering the Atlantic Ocean
COREWAM	Conservation and Research of West African Aquatic Mammals (Senegal)
CS	Case Study
DG EMPL	Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion (EU)
DARE	Direction de l'Aménagement des Ressources et des Etudes
DG ENV	Directorate-General for Environment (EU)
DG INTPA	Directorate-General International Partnerships (EU)
DG MARE	Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (EU)
DG SANTE	Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety (EU)
DG TRADE	Directorate-General for Trade (EU)
DWF	Distant Water Fleet
EAF	Ecosystem Approach to Fisheries
EAFM	Ecosystem Approach to Fisheries Management
EBCD	European Bureau for Conservation and Development
EU	European Union
EUROPÊCHE	Association of National Organizations of Fishing Enterprises in the EU
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
ERS	Electronic Recording Systems
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FPAOI	Federation of Artisanal Fishermen of Indian Ocean
ICCAT	International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tuna
IEO	Instituto Español de Oceanografía
ILO	International Labour Organization
IMAR	Instituto do Mar (former INDP-Cape Verde)
IMO	International Maritime Organisation
IMROP	Institut Mauritanien de Recherches Océanographiques et des Pêches
ISRA-CRODT	Oceanographic Research Centre of Dakar-Thiaroye
IUU	Illegal, Unreported, and Unregulated fishing

LDAC	EU Long Distance Fleet Advisory Council
MATIS	Icelandic Food and Biotech R & D Institute
MCS	Monitoring, Control and Surveillance
MSC	Marine Stewardship Council
MAPA	Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación
MFMR	Ministry of Fisheries and Marine Resources
MPEM	Ministère des Pêches et de l'Économie Maritime
OPROMAR	Organización de Productores de Pesca Fresca del Puerto y Ría de Marín
PCD	Policy Coherence for Development
PFA	Pelagic Freezer Association
PRCM	Regional Partnership for Coastal and Marine Conservation
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organisation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SFA	Seychelles Fisheries Authority
SFP	Sustainable Fisheries Partnership
SFPA	Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement
SSNC	Swedish Society for Nature Conservation
SSF	Small Scale Fisheries
UCAM	Université Cadi Ayyad
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
UNCTAD	United Nations Conference on Trade and Development
USP	Universidade de São Paulo
WWF	World Wide Fund for Nature

1 Introduction

Whenever the EU Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) comes under review (next review is expected 2022), the relevance of the external and international dimension is permanently called into question, casting doubts on whether they are properly integrated within the CFP, evaluating their coherence with other EU policies and estimating their conformity and consistency with the international law of the sea (UNCLOS) (Heredia & Oanta, 2015). A crucial piece of this has been to highlight that external branches of the CFP are promoting positive fishing activities by relabelling the Sustainable Fisheries Partnerships Agreements (SFPAs) as ‘sustainable’, which do represent one of the more relevant manifestations of the EU’s international dimension.

According to Article 4(35) of Regulation (EU) No. 1380/2013 on the CFP¹, these international agreements are made by the EU with a third state for the purpose of obtaining access to waters and marine resources (fish stocks) in order to sustainably exploit a share of the surplus of marine biological resources, in exchange for financial compensation and technical support from the EU to the partner countries.

The EU is promoting fisheries agreements for two main reasons:

- 1- The external fisheries policy is designed to maximize employment in the EU fishing sector and ensure a steady supply of fish into EU markets, while limiting pressure on overstressed European ecosystems.
- 2- The EU is the largest market for fish products in the world, with demand for fish in the EU far exceeding the resources available regionally.

SFPAs aim to reflect the EU’s sustainability agenda and “to support developing countries to ensure sustainable fisheries and food security”². The core of the SFPAs is that they respect and strengthen four (4) key principles (Figure 1):

Figure 1: Key principles to take into account when it comes to SFPAs

Source: Authors' own creation

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32013R1380>

² DG Mare (2015). ‘EU helps developing countries to ensure sustainable fisheries and food security.’ Available from: http://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/mare/itemdetail.cfm?item_id=26078

Nevertheless, in a world where fishing resources are exposed to overexploitation and marine habitats face threats derived from human activities and climate change, it is necessary to carry out an unbiased and critical evaluation of the implications of SFPAs as ‘a peace’ of sustainable fisheries into the short and long term, taking into account fisheries sustainability criteria, welfare, coherence with policies and development objectives, transparency and accountability.

Into the last decade, all of these principles have attracted criticism from academics, NGOs, and other institutions, such as the European Parliament and the ACP-EU Joint Assembly³. This has generated several agendas which have been useful to discuss (in different fora), e.g. the suitability of SFPAs as instruments to move towards equitable and sustainable CFP reform (Van den Bossche & Van Der Burgt, 2009).

Over the last four years, the FarFish project has been attempting to add value to the wide debate about the challenges in implementing an adequate policy within the External Dimension of the CFP. The project has organised several workshops, seminars, webinars and international conferences⁴ to address from a critical view, the main pillars of the CFP external dimension. This has also included provision of arguments to support the revision of the next CFP reform.

The FarFish project facilitated an international web conference on June 1st and 2nd 2021 titled **“The External Dimension of the Common Fisheries Policy: Present Challenges and Future Opportunities”**.⁵ The first day was organised in the form of a conference with presentations and panel discussions, and the second day was in the form of a workshop with mixture of presentations, discussions, breakout sessions and round table discussions. This report summarises the discussions and main conclusions of the workshop held on June 2nd, which was titled **“Improving management under fisheries agreements”**.

³ ACP-EU Joint Assembly includes the Members of the European Parliament) and the elected representatives of the African, Caribbean and Pacific states (“ACP countries”, excluding Cuba)

⁴ See: <https://www.farfish.eu/strengthening-fisheries-sustainability-outside-eu/>
<https://www.farfish.eu/bringing-fisheries-sustainability-into-the-high-seasthe-case-of-the-atlantic-south-west-fao41/>
<https://www.farfish.eu/international-conference/>

⁵<https://www.farfish.eu/the-external-dimension-of-the-common-fisheries-policy-present-challenges-and-future-opportunities/>

2 Background

The EU has an enhanced responsibility to promote sustainable and responsible fisheries management in international waters, in its double role as a major fishing player and the largest single market for fisheries products in the world. This is implemented in practice through active participation, where the EU is working closely with other coastal states from around the globe through the United Nations system, including the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO), the International Maritime Organisation (IMO), the UN Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), as well as in Regional Fisheries Management Organisations (RFMOs) and Regional Sea Conventions, and other multiple international and regional bodies. Following these commitments to promote sustainable fisheries, the EU has assumed responsibilities as a contracting party to fisheries agreements. These responsibilities range from the reinforcement of governance, through the creation of evaluations and diagnoses that make it possible to strengthen these agreements by establishing inclusive policies with a real impact on society.

The international dimension of the CFP has increased its visibility and relevance within the last decades, in particular in relation to its coherence and linkages with other EU policies such as cooperation for development, labour, human rights, health and trade issues.⁶

In November 2019, a group of highly relevant institutions and organisations in Africa and Europe⁷ gathered in Brussels to discuss several issues on fisheries sustainability, highlighting how to make SFPAs **'really sustainable'** in order to effectively contribute to the achievement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (CFFA-CAPE, 2020). Some of these discussions included the sustainable management of marine resources, and fish populations, also taking into consideration the necessity to support local fishing communities in order to minimize the impacts generated by fishing activity within the EEZ. In addition, the debate was extended to the inclusion of regional approach for the SFPAs negotiation and implementation, considering that **'marine ecosystems know no borders'**. The messages, recommendations, challenges and opportunities suggested from those key institutions and relevant stakeholders were taken into account when the FarFish project facilitated a web conference in June 2021 in order to facilitate multi-stakeholder discussions on the advantages, disadvantages and current challenges on the External Dimension of the CFP. The focus of the discussions was on the SFPAs as an instrument to strengthen the collaboration among EU and Coastal States.

⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2013:354:0022:0061:EN:PDF>

⁷ Including the Coalition for Fair Fisheries Arrangements (CFFA) and the World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) European networks, BirdLife Europe & Central Asia, the Confédération Africaine des Organisations de Pêche Artisanale (CAOPA), the Coalition Nationale de Plaidoyer Environnemental à Madagascar (CNPE), the Federation of Artisanal Fishermen of Indian Ocean (FPAOI) and the Regional Partnership for Coastal and Marine Conservation (PRCM).

3 Improving Management under Fisheries Agreements

Taking into consideration that both the EU and the coastal States with an SFPA in place must assume their responsibilities to ensure sustainable fisheries management from a collaborative approach, the FarFish workshop on “**Improving management under fisheries agreements**” was mainly focused on cooperational issues, seeing SFPAs as an instrument to strengthen collaboration among EU and Coastal States. The event was organised by Centro Tecnológico del Mar- Fundación CETMAR and the Long-Distance Advisory Council (LDAC), but did also have active participation from other FarFish partners, such as GRO-FTP, Sjókovin, CSIC, Case study leaders from Mauritania, Senegal, Seychelles and Cabo Verde, and more.

3.1 Vision and goals of the event

The event did offer a mix of presentations, panel discussions, breakout sessions, round table discussions and different interventions (some of them supported by visual presentations) to explore **how the CFP External Dimension** can be a **driver for beneficial change** in the field of sustainable fisheries and governance in non-European and international waters, in order to **improve the implementation of the External Dimension of the CFP in the next period (2023-2033)**

3.2 Event objectives

The workshop had a set of general objectives and specific objectives:

❖ General objectives

To discuss the achievements and shortcomings of the current external dimension of the CFP, and to:

- I. Propose measures for enhancing Europe’s role in the International Fisheries Governance (in line with the headline ambition of the European Green Deal).
- II. Discuss how to improve evaluations and transparency of SFPAs, to maximise fishing opportunities for operators and use of sectorial support by the coastal States.
- III. Recommend ways to strengthen EU input and influence in the RFMOs.
- IV. Reflect on mechanisms to achieve sustainable management and conservation measures in non-EU waters, through a level playing field among all operators and better coordination and implementation of international legal instruments related to human activities and pressures in the seas.

❖ Specific objectives

- i. To open a critical and accurate discussion about achievements and shortcomings of the External Dimension of the CFP, particularly at the SFPAs level.
- ii. To initiate a dialogue to identify the main findings, strengths and weaknesses of SFPAs, as international cooperation tools between the EU and third countries.
- iii. To communicate advances, lessons learnt, challenges and needs on scientific cooperation between the EU and coastal countries with a SFPAs in place, from the FarFish project experience.

3.3 The agenda

The workshop was divided into two different panels from the most general to the specific (see agenda in Figure 2):

Figure 2: Agenda for the second-day event, 'Improving Management under Fisheries Agreements'

The agenda was designed on the following criteria:

A) In relation to the content:

- i. To link cooperation as an essential mechanism for progress and advancement in the design and implementation of the future of SFPAs.
- ii. To establish gradual contents that start from general aspects that could be specified in more specific and operational aspects.
- iii. To bring case experiences where the application of a practical and real cooperation approach between different user profiles could be substantiated and noted (exemplified among others, in the FarFish case studies).

B) In relation to the profiles:

- i. To find a balance in the participation of different user profiles, from pools, through coastal authorities, scientists, NGOs with an impact on local communities.
- ii. To establish a clear gender approach not just to ensure the gender balance within the webinar participation, but to promote a critical reflection around the inequalities that derive from the process of gender construction in specific social, geographical, cultural, ethnic and historical contexts.

Thus, during **Panel I**, the main challenges facing the implementation of SFPAs were discussed, taking into account the advantages and weaknesses of evaluating the SFPAs.

Along with **Panel II**, contributions and practical views from FarFish Case Studies with an SFPA in place (Mauritania, Senegal, Seychelles and Cabo Verde) were discussed considering the information as follows⁸:

- SFPAs in numbers
 - Main numbers: Fishing opportunities and fishing access: relevant changes comparing with previous protocols
 - Contributions (social and economic) to national development
- Sectoral support
 - Fisheries programmes and actions derived from this aid
 - Evidences, challenges and needs (advantages and disadvantages)
- Synergies between SFPAs and other EU policies
 - IUU, trade, capacity building, cooperation for development, labour and social aspects
- Conclusions:
 - Challenges and needs

3.4 Attendees

During two days (June 1st and 2nd, 2021), high level experts and key stakeholders from the fishing industry (LDAC, ARVI, ANAMER, OPROMAR, CAOPA, PFA, EUROPECHE, CEPESCA, ANFACO,...), NGO sectors (CFFA-CAPE, WWF, OCEANA, SFP, MSC, EBCD, SSNC,...) together with relevant EU policy makers (DG MARE, DG RTD, EFCA, EU Parliament), coastal authorities (SFA, MAPA, DARE, DNEM, MFMR), scientists (IMROP, IEO, ISRA-CRODT, COREWAM, UCA, USP,...), international organizations (FAO, COMHAFAT- ATLAFCO), among other relevant actors, gathered to debate about the implementation

⁸ See, FarFish Case Studies Presentations' in ANNEX I.

of the External Dimension of the CFP, the importance, advantages and challenges of the EU role in international fisheries management and ocean governance.

During the second-day workshop on ‘Improving Management under Fisheries Agreements’, a total of 170 people attended from 36 different countries (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Attendees by countries at the second-day

It has to be highlighted how diverse was the stakeholder participation, which has involved different institutions and organizations with distinctive profiles (Figure 4). Beyond the presence of research groups, which is always remarkable, it is good to note the high percentage of members of different government institutions, policy-makers and the fishing industry that have participated in the event. Likewise, the participation of different NGOs deserves mention, acquiring a very proactive role throughout the workshop discussions.

Figure 4: Attendees by institutional profile

It is also important to mention that 75% of the total attendees did not belong to the FarFish Consortium (Figure 4).

Figure 5: Event attendees with direct and indirect ties to the FarFish project

4.2 Main findings

The main findings of the workshop are presented below as general overall observations, and as recommendations for improvements.

The process of preparing these conclusions has been as follows:

1. Generation of a first draft internally (elaborated by CETMAR), including the most relevant discussions that took place during the workshop
2. To submit the first draft to the panellists who either sent back their personal corrections and suggestions to the document, or they just gave us their consent
3. To submit the final version to the moderators both the panel also the round table

❖ Overview

SFPAs are **beneficial instruments** to act as contributors to sustainable fisheries, from the inclusion of relevant cooperation tools which brought beneficial results in terms of fisheries governance.

SFPAs are facilitating the dialogue to improve fisheries policy and specifically to support scientific collaboration and to **promote transparency**.

SFAs are projected towards the generation of **employment** and the development of infrastructures to promote local fishing economies, supporting entrepreneurship diversity.

The incorporation of a clear **gender approach**, which is expected to have positive results in the coming years, is fundamental to promote women empowerment, especially where women play key essential roles in Small Scale Fisheries (SSF), local fishing economy, household livelihoods and nutrition.

SFPAs are encouraging a progressive job inspection in order to **enhance labour conditions** according to International Labour Organization (ILO) standards, including clauses on human rights. Also, SFPAs are incorporating conditions to strengthen transparency, essential rights and sustainability.

SFPAs have contributed to the development of **institutional capacity** (financing of training, research and management) also at the level of public investment and National Treasury.

Control and surveillance have been strengthened from the agreements, being an important instrument to **fight against IUU**, through the use of technology and human capacity.

Essential improvements (as follows) to be made for the future of SFPAs **are needed** to respond to the needs of coastal countries and local communities.

❖ **Recommendations**

i) Level playing field and the promotion of the principle of non-discrimination

Same rules must be adopted, including minimum terms and conditions (MTCs), for access to marine resources to all related fleets (e.g. private agreements), in order to extend the conservation standards from Europe to other fishing areas. This is in particular important for shared resources in West Africa, such as small pelagics. The EU and coastal States, with the support of all relevant stakeholders, should build upon the MTCs defined by coastal States to ensure that fishing activities under SFPAs and any arrangement for other DWF are aligned with regional and international standards.

ii) Explore the adoption of a regional approach to strengthening collaboration

A regional approach should be developed in coherence with other environmental and social regional initiatives, as well as with Regional Fisheries Management Organisations' (RFMOs) regulations, adopting joint management measures to better monitor fishing activities in EEZs, in order to strengthen conservation and management measures at the regional level.

An efficient regional monitoring and surveillance system can contribute to a more harmonised scientific knowledge to enhance understanding of interconnected marine ecosystems, cost-effective MCS and compliance. EU should support coastal States in reinforcing regional cooperation to align with best practices worldwide.

iii) Improve data collection, particularly on assessing impacts of fishing activity on marine ecosystems, fisheries and coastal communities

Based on the best science-based knowledge, EU and coastal States should ensure that scientific data has been collected to clearly define and clarify the existence of a 'surplus'. Socio-economic knowledge should be increased, and socio-economic data collected to enable for improved impact assessments.

Quantitative, qualitative and gender-disaggregated data should also be compiled jointly on the socio-economic aspects of the fisheries, including incomes along the different value chains, employment conditions and jobs generated, social change analysis, contribution to national nutrition needs, etc.

In addition, it is relevant to promote joint scientific research adapted to the reality of shared stocks, improving stock assessment and promoting transparency and accessibility on scientific data.

iv) Encourage an increased relevant stakeholder participation, including civil society, in all discussions and implementation processes for fair and sustainable agreements

Although the CFP Regulation states that the SFPAs "*shall be in the mutual interest of the Union and the third countries concerned, including their local populations and fishing industry*" (Art. 31.2, 1380/2013), and that they allow "*to establish the governance framework, including [...] promoting the consultation processes of interest groups*" (Art. 32.1.b....), SFPAs have still low participation rates of civil society, being negotiated without appropriate consultation with all stakeholders, particularly when it does refer to coastal States. It is therefore needed to increase the engagement of civil society in SFPA negotiations and implementation processes, incorporating incentives to encourage especially the participation of the local fishing sector to adapt what is accorded to the local reality, evaluating the impacts of their compliance.

The coastal States and the EU should make sure that all relevant stakeholders at local, regional and national levels are systematically and transparently consulted. In addition, EU should guarantee the support to coastal States in initiating an internal governance process to draw up national plans, implementing different mechanisms to improve the communication with civil society in order to strengthen the agreements

v) Improve alignment of SFPAs with the coastal State's national strategies within a global and international framework to fit with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and European environmental requirements, complying with the Policy Coherence for Development (PCD).

There is a clear weakness when it comes to aligning SFPAs with the coastal state's objectives stated into the national development strategies, specially to tackle global challenges like climate change, food security and their impacts on fisheries and coastal communities.

EU and Coastal States should guarantee that all SDG targets, as well as the aspects of the 2019 United Nations General Assembly Resolution 74.18 related to agreement negotiations, are well inserted in SFPAs⁹.

vi) Strength the SFPAs evaluation processes incorporating the experience-based knowledge (EBK) and local institutions as the best approach to identify new indicators to efficiently address local challenges.

Although the SFPA evaluation (ex-ante and ex-post evaluations) are an optimal tool to assess the impact in the third country of the various EU policies affecting fisheries in the third countries concerned, the content of the evaluations could be improved.

Indicators (quantitative and qualitative) as part of these evaluations should be more clearly identified to explicitly assess the various aspects of SFPAs, including fishing and environmental impacts, among their contribution to achieving the SDGs.

The inclusion of different organizations (NGOs) and coastal State's national research institutions will be very useful in order to link the contributions developed by these entities in previous investigations and their adaptation into the SFPAs evaluations.

Adequate resources should be invested to collect relevant and necessary data to develop all these indicators.

vii) Improve EU policy coherence through the promotion of capacity building through the identification of training needs by coastal States and reinforcement into the SFPAs agreements and protocols

Capacity building and training are some of the most relevant actions to improve professional skills, competencies and knowledge-transfer for a wide variety of groups and profiles within the field of fisheries management. There is an evident lack of training programs and capacity building opportunities, especially for managers and technicians to support EU policy coherence and decision-making; this presents a clear imbalance, as institutions from different coastal States do not possess the same resources.

It is needed to increase the technical and human capabilities, particularly in those coastal States with limited resources, to advance in the development of scientific research, to improve monitoring, control and surveillance and to advance into the regional approach (EC, 2009).

⁹ <https://undocs.org/en/A/RES/74/18>

viii) SFPA sectoral support is key to institutional capacity building if it is able to connect to real needs and interest from the partner coastal States

Sectoral support is an essential part of the financial contribution to advance towards the development of sustainable fisheries; and capacity building is one of the most relevant actions to improve professional skills, competencies and knowledge-transfer for a wide varied of groups and profiles within the field of fisheries governance.

The coastal States and EU must ensure that sectoral support is contributing to the national development strategy, protecting vulnerable local fishing communities and ensuring long-term sustainable fisheries management. It is pretty common to see abandoned and uncontrolled infrastructures (so-called 'White Elephants') due to deficient design which does not adjust to the needs, interests and possibilities of the coastal States.

The EU and coastal States should promote transparency and participatory processes when the identification of supporting spending priorities; it does imply the involvement of the whole stakeholder community, including women as the main processors within local fishing communities.

ix) Rethinking the financial structure at sectoral support execution, avoiding rigidity through the inclusion of flexibility mechanisms

Sectoral support has to be planned and executed based on an efficient financial management plan. There is an urgent necessity to improve flexibility and adaptability. Different mechanisms should be taken in place in order to facilitate the extension and renewal of the financial support via an SFPA. Thus, the identification of the budget value and spending period could be more flexible if the objectives previously identified have been achieved or at least a short-term roadmap developed by the coastal State.

It is important to identify the relevant stakeholders in the coastal States for them to be directly benefited from this support. Mechanism for periodic monitoring of the use of these funding could include training sessions and structured dialogues, such as monitoring committees that assess the spending (Panossian, 2020).

x) The promotion of initiatives for partnership between science and fishing industry are essential to generate entrust, bringing science to fishers.

Understanding fishers from data-provider to real players involved in science is essential if we want to move forward with fisheries sustainability. Inclusion of fishers in the design and implementation of scientific activities is also crucial to get better scientific knowledge.

Within the framework of FarFish, some initiatives were implemented between scientists and the fishing industry (e.g. implementation of a self-sampling pilot program for EU and national fleet in Senegalese and Mauritanian EEZ) which enriched the data transference. Therefore, FarFish was presented as a valuable Stakeholder Hub to strength scientific cooperation at the coastal country level within the framework of the SFPAs.

xi) Encourage networking between EU programmes and partnerships from the fisheries sector, also reinforcing cooperation with other DGs (...) to ensure coherence and consistency

The EU should ensure that the implementation of SFPAs is enhanced with development policy to be aligned with the Policy Coherence for Development. Coordination between different DGs (MARE, INTRA, TRADE, SANTE or EMPL) is needed in order to assure policy inter-coherence promoting an efficient use of financing by promoting transparency and strengthening capacities.

4 Conclusions

The workshop on “Improving Management under Fisheries Agreements” developed within the framework of the FarFish project aimed to update some of the most relevant discussions that taken place on different forums regarding the suitability of SFPAs as instruments for promoting fisheries sustainability to advance into the upcoming CFP reform.

From a general view, the outcomes taken from the discussions have described a relatively optimistic balance for SFPAs as contributors to sustainable fisheries. Nevertheless, there is still room to improve, especially in order to respond to the needs and interests of coastal states and local communities.

Many of the conclusions formulated during the workshop have assisted the FarFish consortium to feed into a position paper that was submitted to the EC public consultation procedure aimed to inform the revision process of the CFP towards 2022.

In addition, some of these recommendations described in the current document, are feeding the creation of a policy brief¹⁰ that will be presented at the final FarFish meeting in mid-November 2021, as a new opportunity to generate a strategic document that efficiently encompasses concrete responses and actions towards the CPF review.

¹⁰ See ‘FarFish D1.4 - Policy brief on the CFP external dimension towards 2022’ <https://www.farfish.eu/farfish-deliverables/>

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ANNEX I

Case study leaders' presentations

CONFERENCE ON THE EXTERNAL DIMENSION OF THE COMMON FISHERIES POLICY: PRESENT CHALLENGES AND FUTURE OPPORTUNITIES

Round table – FarFish Case Studies –
1 - 2 June 2021

Benvindo Fonseca, IMar, Cabo Verde

SFPA, EU – Cabo Verde

Protocol of application of the Fisheries Agreement
2019-2024, decree law n° 9/2019 of October 28th

Why a SFPA

Main Features

- **Valid for a period of 5 years**
- **Only for tuna and tuna like species**
- **Total of 69 EU fishing vessels;(28 pursainers, 14 pull and line vessels and 27 long liners)**
- **Counterpart of 3,750,000 (three million, seven thousand and five hundred euros).**

What's new in the protocol?

- **Scientific Studies**
 - Scientific commission to elaborate studies, assessment and partnerships whenever there is any evidence of overexploitation of the stocks or species non declared in the protocol
- **Sectoral Support**
 - Increase of the sectorial support, improve the development of the coastal communities, modernizing the fishing activities of the national fishermen improving safety at sea and socio-economic development of the fisheries

- **SDGs (SDG 14)**
- **Blue Economy**
- **New cooperation mechanisms**
- Sensibilise the European Operators take benefits of the industrial and commercial opportunities of the fisheries sector and maritime economy in Cabo Verde

FarFish Relevant Tasks

- Stakeholder Hub implementation
- Harmonization report system
- Develop MRs in accordance with the responsive fisheries management system (RFMS) approach;
- Farfish-DLMtool and Data limited methods course
- Tuna Value chain analyse
- Fisheries training Programme, MRI (2 IMar Researcher benefited)
- Measuring socioeconomic impacts of the SFPA

Recommendations / Challenges

- Put in place the system for automatically receiving e-logbook data from EU vessels (in 2021). Make use of SFPA
- Put in place the requirement for all foreign vessels to use an electronic reporting system that can communicate with the system envisaged for Cabo Verde (by 2025)
- In the context of ICCAT, call for the harmonisation of data collection from tuna fisheries (logbook templates). Work towards implementing existing proposals (section on final considerations) by 2025.
- Implement the observer programme and a self-sampling (or logbook scheme) proposed for Cabo Verde national fisheries and allocate SFPA sector support funding for this (2021-2025).

Thank you very much

benvindo.fonseca@imar.gov.cv

www.farfish.eu

**THE EXTERNAL DIMENSION OF THE
COMMON FISHERIES POLICY:
PRESENT CHALLENGES AND FUTURE OPPORTUNITIES**
1st -2nd June 2021

**Accords de pêche Mauritanie-
Union européenne**

CAMARA LAMINE

Introduction

La Mauritanie appartient l'écosystème des Canaries, l'un des quatre grands écosystèmes d'upwelling parmi les plus productifs du monde.

Cet atout majeur fait que la Mauritanie dispose, sous sa juridiction des hotspots de biodiversité et une richesse halieutique exceptionnelle permettant de contribuer de manière significative à son développement économique et social.

**Fisheries -
conservation
hotspots**

TRENDS in Ecology & Evolution

Introduction

- Très tôt, juste après l'indépendance, la Mauritanie s'est orientée vers l'exploitation de cette ressource halieutique
- Mais des obstacles majeurs : absence d'infrastructure, de tradition maritime, de moyens techniques et financiers et faiblesse du marché intérieur;
- Recours aux flottilles étrangères inévitables : licences libres, sociétés mixtes et accord de pêche bilatéral ou multilatéral

Accords de pêche avec la Chine, de l'Union européenne, la Russie, le Japon, du Sénégal

Accords de pêche, signé avec l'Union européenne qui ont débuté en 1987, sont les plus importants.

Le dernier accord toujours en vigueur est celui de 2015-2019. Il prévoit :

- ✓ Une contre partie financière annuelle de cinquante-cinq (55) millions d'euros pour l'accès des navires de l'Union européenne à la zone de pêche mauritanienne
- ✓ Un appui sectoriel pour la promotion d'une pêche durable s'élève à seize (16) millions d'euros pour la période du protocole et une redevance de 2% en nature de la part de chalutiers pélagiques congélateurs et crevettiers

Introduction

Comparativement aux protocoles précédents, dans le dernier accord RIM-UE:

- Ajout d'une nouvelle catégorie 2bis, pour des chalutiers congélateurs ciblant le merlu noir avec possibilité de pêche des calamars et seiches
- Des dépassements sont autorisés à hauteur de 10% sans incidence sur la contrepartie financière versée par l'UE, dans les catégories : chalutiers congélateurs de pêche pélagique, merlu tiers; thoniers

A titre d'information pour ce qui des possibilités de pêche :

Dans le cadre du protocole 2015-2019, les possibilités de pêche sont :

- ✓ 225 000 tonnes de petits pélagiques
 - ✓ 5 000 tonnes de crevettes
 - ✓ 6 000 tonnes de merlu noir
 - ✓ 3 000 tonnes d'espèces démersales autres que le merlu
- un tonnage de référence de 20 000 tonnes pour les thoniers.

Cependant, les retombées économiques et sociales sont faibles

Sectoral support

Les accords de pêche, à travers l'appui sectoriel, contribuent au développement :

- ✓ De la surveillance
- ✓ Des connaissances scientifiques
- ✓ des infrastructures
- ✓ De la conservation de la biodiversité et de l'environnement
- ✓ Des capacités humaines à travers des Formations et stages
- ✓ De l'hygiène et la salubrité des produits halieutiques
- ✓ De l'aménagement des ressources

Cependant, les montants destinés à l'appui sectoriel ont beaucoup baissé lors des deux derniers accords. En effet, de 16 millions d'euros par an (2008-2012) nous sommes passés à :

- **Trois (3) millions d'euros annuel en 2012-2014;**
- **Seize (16) millions d'euros pour toute la période du protocole 2015-2019**

Synergies between SFPAs and other EU policies

Le protocole d'accord Mauritanie-UE 2015-2019 est le premier qui contient des engagements détaillés en faveur de la transparence

D'une manière générale, les accords de pêche RIM-UE, respectent la durabilité de la ressource, car conclus sur le reliquat de la ressource non exploitée

La mise en œuvre de ces accords est accompagnée par un comité scientifique conjoint afin d'assurer la durabilité de la ressource exploitée et l'intégrité des écosystèmes

La législation européenne exige des navires de l'Union à mettre en place des mesures permettant l'évitement des captures accidentelles des espèces vulnérables

Cependant, dans aucun des accords, il n'est fait mention de mesures d'atténuation des prises accidentelles des espèces vulnérables telles que les Mammifères marins, les Tortues et oiseaux de mer.

Conclusions

- ❑ L'accord de partenariat en matières de pêches avec l'UE reste le plus important aussi bien en termes de possibilité de pêche accordées qu' en terme de diversité d'espèces exploitées
- ❑ C'est le seul accord avec la RIM à être accompagné par un comité scientifique pour assurer la durabilité de la ressource et l'intégrité des écosystème
- ❑ Malgré une réduction des possibilités de pêche depuis 2012 (exclusion des céphalopodiers et des langoustiers) , les avantages économiques perçus par la Mauritanie sont restés acceptables (67 millions d'Euros en 2012-2014 et 55 millions d'Euros en 2015-2019)

Cependant, le désengagement progressif de l'Union européenne en matière de subvention, sous la pression des ONG et de l'OMC qui avait pour but de limiter la surexploitation et la dissipation de la rente peut poser trois problèmes majeurs qui méritent des études approfondies :

Conclusions

- ✓ La subvention permettait de maintenir les prix des petits pélagiques à la portée des millions d'ouest africains que la pêche artisanale locale mauritanienne et même sénégalaise ne peut pas approvisionner pour diverses raisons (demande intérieure, qualité du produit, quantités mises en jeu, transport, prix...);
- ✓ Le manque de subvention risque de pousser les pêcheurs à surexploiter davantage la ressource pour espérer rentabiliser leur outil de production;
- ✓ Les autres flottilles étrangères seraient emmenées à s'aligner sur les redevances payées par les armateurs européens qui disposent de meilleurs avantages comparatifs.
- ✓ Le montant de l'aide et sa nature doivent répondre aux besoins réels du secteur de la pêche en Mauritanie et provenir du fonds de développement (l'union européenne se considère comme le premier donateur à l'échelle internationale) même en l'absence d'accords.

Je vous remercie de
votre attention

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**THE EXTERNAL DIMENSION OF THE
COMMON FISHERIES POLICY:
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1st -2nd June 2021

Table ronde
Etude de cas : Sénégal

Mamadou Diallo, Ndiaga Thiam et Fambaye Ngom Sow

Introduction

Le premier accord de pêche bilatéral de l'UE a été conclu avec le Sénégal 1979

- Accord mixte donne accès à un large éventail de stocks de poissons dans la ZEE sénégalaise
- Cet accord mixte a été appliqué jusqu'en 2006, au moyen d'une série de protocoles offrant aux navires de l'UE la possibilité d'accéder aux ressources halieutiques du Sénégal

Changement de paradigme en Europe...

Réforme de la PCP de l'UE en décembre 2002

- Transformation des anciens régimes d'accès assortis d'une contrepartie financière en partenariats en faveur de l'instauration d'une pêche responsable et durable (accords de partenariat dans le domaine de la pêche ou APP)
- Nouveaux accords de pêche (accords de partenariat pêche et de seconde génération) cherchent à mieux équilibrer la part respective des accords commerciaux, des actions de développement et des accords de pêche, et à créer de nouvelles formes d'associations permettant une coopération plus durable en tenant compte de l'accroissement des capacités de pêche des États tiers

Nouveau cadre de référence au Sénégal...

1. *Plan Sénégal Emergent* (PSE) : qui fixe les orientations stratégiques et d'intervention du gouvernement, des partenaires, du secteur privé et de la société civile pour la période 2014-2035
2. *Lettre de Politique Sectorielle de Développement de la Pêche et de l'Aquaculture*, (LPSDPA) : qui fixe les priorités spécifiques et les actions à entreprendre dans le secteur entre 2016-2023

Désormais...

En 2014, transformation en accord thonier, avec un volet relatif aux poissons démersaux (merlu noir), conclu pour cinq ans et tacitement reconductible. Cet accord était accompagné d'un protocole qui s'étale de 2019 à 2024

Accord de partenariat de pêche durable UE-Sénégal et son protocole de mise en œuvre

Premier protocole

Période : 2014-2019

- 28 thoniers senneurs congélateurs,
- 10 canneurs
- 5 palangriers d'Espagne, de Portugal et de France,
 - ✓ tonnage de référence de 14 000 tonnes de thon
 - ✓ 2000 tonnes de merlu noir pour deux chalutiers espagnols par

Le Sénégal reçoit une compensation de 15 millions d'euros ainsi qu'une assistance technique de la part de l'UE

Deuxième protocole

Période : 2020-2024

- 28 thoniers senners congélateurs,
- 10 canneurs
- 5 palangriers d'Espagne, de Portugal et de France,
 - ✓ tonnage de référence de 10 000 tonnes de thon
 - ✓ 1750 tonnes de merlu noir pour deux chalutiers espagnols

La contrepartie financière annuelle de l'UE s'élève à 1,7 million d'euros dont 800 000 euros pour les droits d'accès aux eaux du Sénégal et 900 000 euros pour l'appui sectoriel

Appui sectoriel

Mise en œuvre de la LPSDPA et développement de l'économie maritime

- gestion durable des ressources
- **amélioration du suivi, du contrôle et de la surveillance des activités de la pêche**
- **développement des capacités scientifiques, la recherche sur les ressources halieutiques et la collecte des données**
- soutien à la pêche artisanale
- développement de l'aquaculture
- valorisation, le contrôle et la certification sanitaire des produits de la pêche
- renforcement des acteurs du secteur

Synergies

- ✓ lutte contre la pêche INN :
 - amélioration du suivi, du contrôle et de la surveillance des activités de la pêche
- ✓ Aspects sociaux et d'emploi :
 - soutien aux pêcheries artisanales
- ✓ renforcement des capacités :
 - développement des capacités scientifiques dans le secteur halieutique
 - renforcement des acteurs du secteur

Conclusions

- ❖ Gestion des ressources de façon durable
- ❖ Suivi périodique des accords en fonction de l'état de la ressource
- ❖ Renforcement de la recherche halieutique
- ❖ Augmentation de façon conséquente de la partie financière allouée à la recherche halieutique
- ❖ **Mise en place d'une instance régionale puissante**
- ❖ Mise en place d'un programme national/sous régional d'observateurs
- ❖ Meilleure participation des communautés de pêcheurs

Merci de votre attention

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